

QUALITY INDICATORS OF HONEY SAMPLES COLLECTED FROM VARIOUS REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14993564>

Abstract. *The article presents the results of studies of honey produced in various regions of Uzbekistan, and assesses its quality of natural bee honey according to organoleptic, microscopic and physicochemical indicators.*

Keywords: *monofloral and semi-floral honey, acidity, humidity, hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), pH level, carbohydrates, sample, area, refractometer, quality, evaluation, research, plants, methods.*

I. INTRODUCTION. Honey contains more than 180 substances, including carbohydrates, amino acids, enzymes, proteins, vitamins, minerals, and phenolic compounds, mainly consisting of fructose and glucose. The properties and composition of honey depend on its season, environmental factors, the beekeeper's treatment, and, most importantly, the flower from which the nectar is derived [1, 2]. In many countries, there is a constant high demand for beekeeping products. The high demand can lead to honey adulteration, which can only be identified through laboratory research methods [3, 4]. Modern scientific research methods, such as refractometry, titrimetry, chromatography, and microscopy, allow for the determination of the geographic and botanical origin of honey collected from different regions, as well as its quality. The quality of natural honey depends on organoleptic, microscopic, physical, and chemical indicators. The determination of the hydroxymethylfurfural content allows for identifying its authenticity or whether it has been adulterated [5, 6, 7]. Uzbekistan, due to its natural climatic conditions, is divided into the following regions: steppe, foothill, and mountainous areas (28.3%), irrigated lands (9.6%), and plains and deserts (60.1%). In Uzbekistan, hundreds of species of nectar-producing plants grow, among which several dozen species are of practical importance. These nectar plants are classified according to botanical or agricultural characteristics, flowering period (e.g., spring, summer, autumn), and the growing area or other features [8, 9, 10]. By cultivating plants that bloom at different times, it is possible to collect honey continuously for several months or seasons in one location. In Uzbekistan, beekeepers move their hives to steppe areas with ephemeral plants for honey collection in early spring, to the foothill and mountain areas and irrigated lands at the end of spring and during the summer months [11].

II. RESEARCH METHODS AND SOURCES. The research was conducted as part of the international project "Smart-AI: Application of Intelligent Beekeeping Family System Technology and Development and Improvement of Beekeeping Resources" in collaboration with the Republic of Korea. Honey and propolis samples were collected from beekeeping farms in different regions of Uzbekistan for the identification of products from the beekeeping industry. The samples were sent for laboratory testing to the Andong National University in South Korea. The laboratory "Honey Product Quality Identification" at the university conducted experiments on 43 different samples and compared them with honey standards from Korea.

Figure 1. Honey Samples Collected from Various Regions of Uzbekistan.

The physical and chemical properties of honey were analyzed using modern innovative technologies, including refractometry, titrimetry, chromatography, and microscopy. These scientific research methods were used to determine the geographic and botanical origin of honey collected from different regions, as well as its quality. The quality of natural honey was evaluated based on organoleptic, microscopic, physical, chemical, and hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) indicators.

The quality indicators of honey samples collected from various regions of Uzbekistan were assessed.

The moisture content, acidity, hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), and carbohydrate levels in the honey samples were determined using the following methods.

2 g of honey

75 ml of water

0,2 ml

pH level

To calculate the acidity level of the honey samples, 2 grams of honey were weighed using an Ohaus SPX 6201 KR electronic scale and placed in a 500 ml special measuring beaker. Then, 75 ml of distilled water was added, and the mixture was heated and stirred on a Labtron EVO HS1 heating stirrer until there was no honey left at the bottom of the container. Afterward, 0.2 ml of phenolphthalein indicator was added to the mixture.

Phenolphthalein is used to determine whether the liquid environment is acidic or alkaline based on the pH. When the pH value of the solution changes, phenolphthalein changes color, helping to identify whether the sample is acidic or alkaline. To the prepared solution, a 0.1 molar concentration of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) solution was added using a pipette, and the pH value of the solution was monitored using a HANNA HI 5221 pH meter.

The titration process was stopped when the pH reached 8.3, and the volume of sodium hydroxide (NaOH) used was recorded (in ml).

The acidity of the honey was calculated using the following formula:

$$F = \frac{\text{The volume of NaOH used, (ml)}}{\text{the volume of honey used, gr}} \times 100$$

Moisture Content: To determine the moisture content of honey, the OHAUS MB23 moisture analyzer, which operates at temperatures ranging from +1°C to +100°C, was used. The measurement was conducted at +20°C. Unlike halogen heating elements, infrared heating offers a gentler heating option. During the process, the temperature and time were set, and the drying program was selected from the device's memory. The sample was then placed in a special weighing container, and the process was monitored. The results were recorded on the screen of the MB23 moisture analyzer and printed.

Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) Content: To determine the levels of sucrose, glucose, and fructose in the honey, 5 grams of honey were mixed with 75 ml of water until no honey remained at the bottom of the container. The analysis was carried out using a chromatographic method, and the liquid was analyzed using a chromatography machine.

The obtained data was statistically processed using Student's criteria and according to the method of Ye.K. Merkureva (1970, 1991), with calculations carried out using the MS OFFICE (Microsoft Excel) software and correlated on a computer.

III. RESEARCH RESULTS.

Table 1. Main nectar-producing plants growing in Uzbekistan and regions from which honey samples were collected.

No	The names of the main nectar-producing plants growing in the conditions of Uzbekistan.	The regions from which honey samples were collected.
1	Oily-purslane (Psoralea drupaceae Bunge)	Jizzakh
2		Navoiy
3		Jizzakh
4	Alfalfa (Medicago sativa)	Tashkent
5	Red Clover (Trifolium pratense L.)	Kashkadarya
6	Blue Clover (Medicago sativa L.)	Jizzakh
7	Cotton (Gossypium L.)	Tashkent
8		Jizzakh
9		Jizzakh
10	Sunflower (Helianthus annuus L.)	Tashkent
11		Tashkent
12	Sainfoin (Onobrychis viciaefolia Scop.)	Tashkent
13	Camel Thorn (Alhagi camelorum)	Tashkent
14		Navoiy

15		Navoiy
16		Navoiy
17		Navoiy
18		Navoiy
19		Samarkand
20		Samarkand
21		Samarkand
22		Tashkent
23	Sweet Clover (<i>Melilotus officinalis</i>)	Tashkent
24	Annual and Perennial Herbaceous Plants (<i>Echium bulgare</i> L.)	Andizhan
25		Ferghana
26		Namangan
27		Kashkadarya
28		Sirdarya
29		Samarkand
30		Jizzakh
31		Tashkent
32		Surkhandarya
33	Linden Tree (<i>Tilia</i> L.)	Tashkent
34		Samarkand
35	Willow (<i>Salix coerula</i> Wolf)	Kashkadarya
36		Surkhandarya
37	Maple (<i>Acer</i> L.)	Namangan
38		Namangan
39		Namangan
40	Yellow Acacia (<i>Caragana arborescens</i>)	Tashkent
41		Tashkent
42		Tashkent
43		Jizzakh

Table 2.

Standard Requirements for Honey Quality in the Republic of Korea (COSTR, 52451-2005)

№	Components of Honey	Measurement Unit	In Natural Honey	In Honey Made from Sugar Syrup
1.	Water	%	≤20	≤20
2.	Solids in Water	%	≤0,5	≤0,5
3.	Fructose	%	≤40	≤40
4.	Glucose	%	≤35	≤35
5.	Sucrose	%	≤5	≤5

6.	Hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF)	mg/kg	≤40	≤40
7.	Acidity, ml equivalent per 1 kg	mEk/kg	≤50	≤50
8.	Insoluble substances in water	%	≤1	≤1
9.	Diastase number	Gote	≤8 more	≤8 more
10.	Electrical conductivity	mS.cm	≤0,8	≤0,8
11.	Carbon isotope ratio	%	≤22,5	≤22,5
12.	Alkalinity	pH	≤7	≤7
13.	Isomerized sugar	%	≤0,5	≤0,5

Table 3

Information on the amount of carbohydrates in honey samples collected from various regions of Uzbekistan (average $X \pm S_x$).

No	Name of plant	Fructose, (%) $X \pm S_x$	CV, %	Glucose, % $X \pm S_x$	CV, %	Sucrose $X \pm S_x$	CV, %
1.	Oily-purslane (Psoralea drupaceae Bunge)	40,81±0,72	4,5	26,02±0,29	4,8	0,99±0,25	0,5
2.		38,32±0,92	6,2	35,89±1,70	3,5	1,63±1,67	1,3
3.		38,43±4,62	5,0	28,83±4,08	3,2	0,55±0,96	0,6
4.	Alfalfa (Medicago sativa)	41,25±1,23	4,5	34,94±1,29	4,0	0,91±0,19	0,4
5.	Red Clover (Trifolium pratense L.)	50,46±0,91 *	5,9	26,45±0,8 **	4,8	1,23±0,23 ***	1,2
6.	Blue Clover (Medicago sativa L.)	36,29±5,53	5,2	30,04±4,33	3,5	0,51±0,05	0,4
7.	Cotton (Gossypium L.)	41,00±0,81	5,0	35,56±0,82	4,0	6,38±0,69	4,4
8.		39,07±3,12	3,68	36,18±2,99	3,70	1,85±0,56	0,9
9.		40,30±1,38	3,70	35,57±0,79	3,72	2,56±0,41	1,6
10.	Sunflower (Helianthus annuus L.)	40,45±0,24	3,92	37,40±1,04	3,96	1,66±2,11	1,2
11.		38,50±3,68	4,8	33,74±1,05	6,2	1,10±1,39	1,3
12.	Sainfoin (Onobrychis viciaefolia Scop.)	40,91±0,98	5,2	37,06±1,80	6,4	0,92±0,30	0,8
13.	Camel Thorn (Alhagi camelorum)	40,94±0,20	8,2	35,79±0,64	6,2	3,54±2,65	2,9
14.		40,25±0,80	4,4	37,69±0,46	3,6	3,19±0,31	1,8
15.		38,88±3,94	3,6	31,84±3,50	3,0	2,58±0,79	2,1
16.		42,95±0,98	3,8	36,33±1,18	3,2	3,51±1,30	2,9
17.		40,98±1,65	3,4	37,20±2,54	3,8	1,79±1,04	1,3

18.		42,03±0,54	3,2	37,41±1,56	3,6	2,46±0,85	1,6
19.		39,77±0,97	3,0	36,01±1,49	2,8	0,83±1,25	1,8
20.		38,62±0,84	3,0	35,76±1,31	3,7	1,17±0,80	1,2
21.		38,62±1,52	3,2	33,92±2,87	3,8	4,54±0,43	3,2
22.		41,35±0,90	3,4	36,70±1,95	3,2	0,86±0,21	0,5
23.	Sweet Clover (Melilotus officinalis)	40,42±1,20	3,6	34,92±1,61	3,4	1,42±0,42	0,9
24.	Annual and Perennial Herbaceous Plants (Echium bulgare L.)	34,88±3,14	3,8	30,59±2,12	3,2	1,32±1,04	1,2
25.		35,33±3,17	2,8	30,03±4,20	3,0	2,36±1,50	1,6
26.		37,97±1,01	6,2	30,47±0,99	5,4	5,14±1,63	2,4
27.		39,47±0,93	5,8	33,85±0,33	5,0	2,28±1,41	2,3
28.		42,93±0,82	5,4	36,46±0,44	4,6	1,69±1,07	1,4
29.		37,30±3,30	5,0	32,43±1,92	4,2	0,07±0,13	0,3
30.		41,05±0,60	4,8	34,58±3,10	4,0	0,42±0,38	0,2
31.		41,76±0,40	6,0	35,67±0,37	5,8	1,66±0,63	1
32.		39,30±2,54	5,6	34,90±0,44	4,8	2,14±1,00	1,3
33.		Linden Tree (Tilia L.)	41,67±0,96	5,5	36,12±0,87	4,7	0,48±0,18
34.	37,41±0,29		5,4	33,72±0,45	4,2	4,35±0,85	3,3
35.	Willow (Salix coerulea Wolf)	39,50±0,13 *	4,8	38,13±0,93 **	4,0	4,67±0,36 ***	3,1
36.		34,85±0,25	5,0	29,04±1,02	3,6	4,48±0,66	3,2
37.	Maple (Acer L.)	35,96±2,35	4,4	32,25±1,69	3,8	1,35±0,53	1,1
38.		31,39±7,11	3,8	22,98±1,26	3,0	2,71±1,11	1,8
39.		39,73±2,69	3,0	33,29±2,37	3,7	3,63±1,44	2,6
40.	Yellow Acacia (Caragana arborescens)	38,35±1,73	3,2	35,30±1,45	3,8	1,35±0,80	2,2
41.		38,27±0,20 *	3,4	32,30±0,02 **	3,6	7,44±0,48 ***	4,5
42.		39,14±1,66	3,6	36,35±1,20	3,4	3,50±2,2	2,1
43.		37,43±5,55	3,8	31,54±3,36	3,2	2,65±1,41	1,8

* - P>0,95; ** - P>0,99; *** - P> 0,999

In this table, the amount of carbohydrates in monofloral and polyfloral honey samples collected from various regions of Uzbekistan is presented. The results express the quantities of fructose, glucose, and sucrose as percentages.

Table 4.

Data on the moisture content, hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), and acidity levels of honey samples collected from various regions of Uzbekistan (average X±Sx).

No	Name of plant	Moisture, (%) X±Sx	CV, %	HMF, mg/kg X±Sx	CV, %	Acidity, mEk/kg X±Sx	CV, %
1.	Oily-purslane (Psoralea)	18,53±0,58	5,5	5,41±0,12	1,7	33,3±14,4	3,5
2.		16,00±0,1	5,4	24,92±0,45	4,2	34,21±6,8	3,3
3.		18,60±0,36	4,8	3,23±0,29	1,0	29,9±5,0	3,1

	drupaceae (Bunge)						
4.	Alfalfa (Medicago sativa)	15,25±0,23	5,0	3,54±0,1	0,6	30,4±0,66	3,2
5.	Red Clover (Trifolium pratense L.)	18,67±0,58 *	4,4	44,41±9,35 **	3,8	46,05±5,2 ***	4,1
6.	Blue Clover (Medicago sativa L.)	18,37±0,06	3,8	7,32±0,03	2,0	26,1±2,92	3,8
7.	Cotton	19,00±0,81	3,0	7,72±0,10	3,2	39,63±4,9	3,6
8.	(Gossypium L.)	16,83±0,12	3,2	2,46±0,14	1,8	31,5±2,80	2,2
9.		16,93±0,38	3,4	17,30±0,26	3,6	39,44±5,1	4,5
10.		Sunflower	17,45±0,24	3,6	1,35±0,20	0,4	39,50±5,2
11.	(Helianthus annuus L.)	15,17±0,29	3,8	7,59±0,12	1,2	44,3±4,04	3,2
12.	Sainfoin (Onobrychis viciaefolia Scop.)	17,83±0,6	2,8	6,14±0,30	3,0	41,64±2,5	3,6
13.	Camel Thorn	17,87±0,12	6,2	13,37±1,99	4,4	31,55±5,7	2,4
14.	(Alhagi camelorum)	17,25±0,60	5,8	1,85±0,03	0,6	38,28±7,5	2,3
15.		16,67±0,58	5,4	1,46±0,03	0,4	41,69±7,6	4,4
16.		17,33±0,98	5,0	1,12±0,02	0,2	43,20±2,8	4,3
17.		16,68±0,58	4,8	1,24±0,05	0,4	43,17±7,2	4,2
18.		16,90±0,10	6,0	1,02±0,37	0,8	39,92±5,6	2,3
19.		18,77±0,11	5,6	0,29±0,05	0,8	29,95±5,3	1,3
20.		18,10±0,10	5,5	1,99±0,05	1,7	41,62±2,9	3,5
21.		18,17±0,12	5,4	3,28±0,04	1,2	44,35±2,8	3,3
22.		16,80±0,20	3,4	7,66±0,28	1,2	34,86±8,2	3,5
23.		Sweet Clover (Melilotus officinalis)	17,00±0,20	5,6	2,20±0,35	1,8	38,14±7,6
24.	Annual and	17,67±0,58	3,2	16,02±0,10	2,8	21,65±5,7	2,2
25.	Perennial Herbaceous	20,00±0,17 *	3,8	0,92±0,24 **	0,6	24,91±0,9 ***	2,6
26.	Plants (Echium bulgare L.)	16,33±0,58	4,2	20,54±0,22	4,4	28,11±14	2,4
27.		16,33±0,58	4,8	17,52±0,43	3,0	41,13±5,7	2,3
28.		16,67±0,82	5,0	5,27±0,07	2,6	41,57±7,5	3,4
29.		20,00±0,30 *	5,2	0,71±0,03 **	0,2	33,29±7,6 ***	3,3
30.		18,33±0,58	4,8	3,44±0,10	1,0	34,93±4,3	2,2
31.		18,07±0,06	5,0	1,67±0,17	1,2	46,56±2,4	4,4

32.		20,00±0,30 *	5,6	0,93±0,04 **	0,8	34,90±8,6 ***	3,3
33.	Linden Tree	16,33±0,96	5,5	0,86±0,15	0,7	36,60±2,8	3,5
34.	(Tilia L.)	17,67±0,29	5,4	5,12±0,18	2,2	34,97±5,0	3,3
35.	Willow (Salix coerula Wolf)	18,23±0,13 *	4,8	2,69±0,10 **	2,0	51,57±5,7 ***	3,1
36.		17,13±0,25	5,0	0,97±0,16	0,6	26,62±5,6	3,2
37.	Maple (Acer L.)	16,00±0,35	4,4	2,69±0,33	1,8	46,63±7,6	4,1
38.		19,43±0,06 *	3,8	9,42±0,06 **	3,0	51,59±2,9 ***	4,8
39.		17,73±0,12	3,0	5,31±0,13	2,7	34,63±17	2,6
40.	Yellow Acacia	16,00±0,36	3,2	3,19±0,12	1,8	46,55±7,8	3,4
41.	(Caragana	17,73±0,12	3,4	19,57±0,12	3,6	39,44±5,1	4,5
42.	arborescens)	16,80±0,20	3,6	6,63±0,05	2,1	33,26±2,9	3,4
43.		15,93±5,55	3,8	4,54±3,36	3,2	43,30±16	3,8

* - $P > 0,95$; ** - $P > 0,99$; *** - $P > 0,999$

Table 4. This table presents the moisture content, hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), and acidity levels (m/kg) of monofloral and polyfloral honey samples collected from various regions of Uzbekistan. According to the scientific research results, honey samples from red clover (*Trifolium pretense* L) collected in Navoi region, from willow (*Salix coerula* Wolf) in Kashkadarya region, and from yellow acacia (*Caragana arborescens*) in Tashkent region showed high indicators.

IV. CONCLUSION. We identified significant differences in the productivity of honey samples collected from different regions of Uzbekistan. The diversity of plants and climatic conditions in different regions indicated variations in the levels of carbohydrates, moisture, hydroxymethylfurfural, and acidity in honey.

The carbohydrate content, moisture levels, hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF), and acidity measurements of the monofloral and polyfloral honey samples collected from various regions of Uzbekistan meet the international standards of the Republic of Korea's COSTR 52451-2005, and the GOST 19792-2001 "Natural Honey. Technical Specifications" standards developed by the Russian Federation for CIS countries. These results demonstrate that the honey is of high quality.

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